

Alkali Metals and $[MCl_4]^{2-}$ Structure : Tetrahedral Structure of Cs_2MCl_4 Complexes

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Manuscript received 11 May 1992, accepted 14 October 1993

The complexes of the type Cs_2MCl_4 (where M = Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn and Mg) have distorted tetrahedral structure. Varied distortion from regular tetrahedral geometry is due to the covalent bonding between Cs-Cl. The species $[MCl_4]^{2-}$ ions act as double faced bidentate ligands. The structure has been substantiated by ir spectra and crystal structure data.

In recent years formation of oxygen bridged complexes containing metal complexes as ligand has been a field of interest. Same theory and mode of interpretation have been applied in different fields where the donating sites are halogen atoms.

Observation :

From crystal structure and ir studies of Cs_2MCl_4 complexes, it has been established that all (M = Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn and Mg) are isostructural and the tetrachlorometallate ions $[MCl_4]^{2-}$ are in the form of distorted tetrahedra, but the extent of distortion varies¹. In the case of Cu, it has been reported that crystal consists of hexagonal close packed layers of Cs and Cl atoms with copper in one quarter of the octahedral holes¹.

The structure of tetrachlorometallate(II) ions are of three types : regular, distorted and flattened tetrahedra, and distortion from normal tetrahedral angle may be due to (i) variation of d^n system, (ii) ionic interaction between the ions, or (iii) presence of alkali metals. If the distortion in the tetrahedral symmetry is only due to the variation of d^n system, there would have been some definite regularity, but that has not been observed. And again it has been reported that in all the cases all the four M-Cl bonds are the same¹, i.e. same bond length, thus the possibility of J.T. distortion being responsible for the distortion

is ruled out. However, presence of alkali metals may be one of the factors responsible for the distortion. The negative angle of distortion indicates lengthening of M-Cl bonds whereas positive angle of distortion points towards shortening of M-Cl bonds.

Ir spectra : Terminal $\nu_t(M-Cl)$ stretching frequencies have been assigned in the region 375-300 cm^{-1} , whereas bridging $\nu_b(M-Cl)$ stretching frequencies usually occur below 300 cm^{-1} . Terminal $\nu_t(M-Cl)$ and bridged $\nu_b(M-Cl)$ vibrations of some of the reported complexes are presented in Table 2.

From Table 1, it is very clear that there is definite lowering in the (M-Cl) stretching frequencies of $[MCl_4]^{2-}$ ions compared to terminal $\nu_t(M-Cl)$. In these cases, the coordination number of the central metal ion never goes up. Thus it points towards the alternative that there may be bridging of the type Cs \leftarrow :Cl-M, leading to the elongation of M-Cl bond length.

TABLE 1

Compd.	Structure	Angle of distortion* (degree)	ν_{M-Cl} cm^{-1}
Cs_2MgCl_4	Distorted tetrahedra ^a	-	-
$(Me_4N)_2MnCl_4$	-	-	284s ^b
$(Et_4N)_2MnCl_4$	-	-	284s ^b

Table-1. (Contd.)

(Ph ₃ MeAs) ₂ MnCl ₄	-	-	272 ^s ^h
Cs ₂ FeCl ₄	Distorted tetrahedra ^b	-	284 ⁱ
(Me ₄ N) ₂ FeCl ₄	-	-	284 ^s ^g
(Et ₄ N) ₂ FeCl ₄	-	-	286 ^s ^g
(Ph ₃ MeAs) ₂ FeCl ₄	-	-	272 ^s ^h
Cs ₂ CoCl ₄	Distorted tetrahedra ^c	-	298 ⁱ
(Me ₄ N)CoCl ₄	-	2.9	296 ^g
(Et ₄ N) ₂ CoCl ₄	-	-3.9	297 ^s ^g
(Ph ₃ MeAs) ₂ CoCl ₄	-	-	284 ^s ^h
Cs ₂ NiCl ₄	Regular tetrahedra at high temperature ^d	-	-
(Et ₄ N) ₂ NiCl ₄	-	-3.0	289 ^s ^g
(Phe ₃ MeAs) ₂ NiCl ₄	-	-	275 ^s ^h
Cs ₂ CuCl ₄	Flattened tetrahedra ^e	15.0	265 ⁱ
(Me ₄ N) ₂ CuCl ₄	-	20.0	281 ^g
(Et ₄ N) ₂ CuCl ₄	-	-	267 ^s ^g
(Ph ₃ MeAs) ₂ CuCl ₄	-	-	283 ^s ^h
Cs ₂ ZnCl ₄	Distorted tetrahedra ^f	5.9	279 ⁱ
(Me ₄ N) ₂ ZnCl ₄	-	2.2	276 ^s ^g
(Et ₄ N) ₂ ZnCl ₄	-	-	277 ^s ^g
(Ph ₃ MeAs) ₂ ZnCl ₄	-	-	262 ^s ^h

*Ref. 10. ^aRefs. 2, 3. ^bRefs. 4, 5. ^cRef. 6. ^dRef. 7. ^eRef. 8. ^fRef. 9. ^gRef. 11. ^hRef. 12. ⁱRef. 1.

TABLE 2

Compd.*	Monomer $\nu_t(\text{M-Cl})$ cm^{-1}	Polymer $\nu_b(\text{M-Cl})$ cm^{-1}
Co(Py) ₂ Cl ₂	347	186
Co[4-Cl(Py)] ₂ Cl ₂	318	185
Co[4-Br(Py)] ₂ Cl ₂	318	185

*Ref. 13.

Crystal structure data : Reported crystal structure data regarding Cs-Cl distances are listed in Table 3.

TABLE 3

Compd.	Cs-Cl distance (Å), in compounds observed by X-ray
Cs ₂ MgCl ₄ ^a	3.595, 3.522, 3.492, 3.482, 3.467
Cs ₂ FeCl ₄ ^b	3.93, 3.67, 3.49
Cs ₂ CoCl ₄ ^c	3.94, 3.69, 3.52, 3.50
Cs ₂ CuCl ₄ ^d	3.63, 3.47, 3.43, 3.42
Cs ₂ ZnCl ₄ ^e	3.94, 3.67, 3.49

^aRef. 3. ^bRefs. 4, 5. ^cRef. 6. ^dRef. 8. ^eRef. 9.

Sum of the ionic radii of the Cs-Cl is 3.50 Å whereas sum of the van der Waals atomic radii is 4.25 Å. From Table 3, it is quite obvious that distance between Cs-Cl is less than the sum of van der Waals atomic radii of Cs and Cl atoms and even at some places it is less than sum of the ionic radii. Thus it can be concluded that Cs and Cl atoms distance is very close, i.e. there is some sort of covalent bonding between the two in the case of Cs₂MCl₄ complexes.

Conclusion : Stability trend of the complexes of Cs₂MCl₄ type does not follow Irving-Williams rule¹⁴. It can be suggested that the presence of alkali metal is responsible for the distortion. From Table 3, it is quite obvious that Cs and Cl atoms are very close, i.e. there is some sort of covalent bonding between the two in the case of Cs₂MCl₄ complexes.

Due to the presence of alkali metal Cs, linked covalently with Cl atoms, the [MCl₄]²⁻ tetrahedra experience pressure from all sides and thereby get distorted. The extent of distortion depends upon the degree of covalent bonding of Cs-Cl bond. More the covalent Cs-Cl bond is, the more is the distortion, because [MCl₄]²⁻ ions get more pressurised.

From ir data (Table 1), it is clear that M-Cl stretching frequencies of Cs₂MCl₄ type complexes correspond to bridged stretching frequencies. Thus in Cs₂MCl₄ type complexes Cs is coordinated to Cl atoms, i.e. [MCl₄]²⁻ ion acts as ligand and there exists a bond of the type M-Cl:→Cs.

Structure : Structure of the complexes has been suggested as

The structure is polymeric and coordination number of Cs would be more than two.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (A.C.V.) is thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for awarding Junior and Senior Research Fellowships.

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